

DAILY VS. ALTERNATE-DAY ORAL IRON THERAPY IN THE MANAGEMENT OF IRON DEFICIENCY ANEMIA

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Abstract

Background:

Iron deficiency anemia (IDA) remains a major global and national health burden, particularly in low- and middle-income countries such as Pakistan. Conventional daily oral iron therapy is limited by gastrointestinal intolerance and hepcidin-mediated reductions in absorption. This study compares daily versus alternate-day oral iron supplementation over eight weeks in adults with IDA, evaluating hemoglobin response, ferritin recovery, tolerability, and adherence. The findings aim to inform evidence-based iron replacement strategies in high-prevalence settings.

Materials and Methods:

This comparative cross-sectional study enrolled 120 adults with iron deficiency anemia, randomly assigned to receive either daily ($n = 60$) or alternate-day ($n = 60$) oral iron for eight weeks. Hemoglobin and serum ferritin were measured at baseline and follow-up, while adherence and gastrointestinal adverse events were monitored. Data were analyzed to compare hematologic response, iron store replenishment, tolerability, and compliance between the two regimens. All data was entered and calculated using SPSS version 23.0. The statistical significance set at $p \leq 0.05$.

Results:

Among 120 adults with iron deficiency anemia, baseline demographic and hematologic characteristics were comparable between the daily and alternate-day iron groups. After eight weeks, alternate-day therapy resulted in a significantly greater hemoglobin increase (+2.1 vs. +1.3 g/dL, $p < 0.001$) and higher ferritin levels (median 40 vs. 32 ng/mL, $p = 0.012$), with more patients achieving an Hb rise ≥ 2 g/dL (58.3% vs. 33.3%, $p = 0.007$). Gastrointestinal adverse events were less frequent with alternate-day dosing (13.3% vs. 30.0%, $p = 0.028$), while adherence remained high and comparable between groups.

Conclusion:

Alternate-day oral iron therapy in adults with iron deficiency anemia produced superior hemoglobin and ferritin responses and fewer gastrointestinal adverse

events compared with daily dosing. Its simplicity, safety, and effectiveness make it a practical strategy for routine clinical use, though further studies are warranted to optimize dosing across diverse populations.

INTRODUCTION

Iron deficiency anemia (IDA) remains one of the most common nutritional disorders globally and contributes substantially to morbidity and mortality.¹ According to the World Health Organization, about 1.62 billion people, nearly 25% of the world's population, are estimated to be anemic, and iron deficiency is a leading cause.² In children under five, and women of reproductive age (WRA), the burden is especially high.³ Despite numerous public health efforts, the prevalence has declined slowly, and many regions still face moderate to severe levels.⁴

In Pakistan, the situation is no less concerning. Findings from the National Nutrition Survey (NNS) 2018 indicate that 28.9% of children under five (CU5) and 18.4% of WRA suffer from IDA.⁵ Earlier surveys showed even higher figures: in children under five, prevalence ranged between 40-70% in various districts; non-pregnant women aged 15-49 had an IDA prevalence of about 18.1% in NNS 2011-12, while earlier smaller studies reported figures up to 30-60% in specific communities.⁶ These substantial rates are associated with adverse outcomes including impaired cognitive and physical development in children, preterm birth, reduced productivity, and worsened quality of life among adults.^{7,8}

The standard of care for IDA involves oral iron supplementation, usually given daily, often in the form of ferrous salts.⁹ However, daily oral iron is frequently associated with poor tolerability, particularly gastrointestinal adverse events, and suboptimal absorption when doses are repeated on consecutive days.¹⁰ Recent biochemical studies have demonstrated that oral iron increases hepcidin, a regulatory peptide that reduces further iron absorption for approximately 24 hours after exposure, attenuating incremental gains when iron is given daily.¹¹ These findings have led to the hypothesis that alternate-day dosing may reduce hepcidin suppression, improve fractional iron absorption, lessen side

effects, and possibly improve both hematologic response and replenishment of iron stores.¹²

Several randomized controlled trials (RCTs) have begun to test this hypothesis. Despite accumulating evidence, there remain gaps: many trials have focused on specific subpopulations (children, pregnant women, or women of reproductive age), limited durations (4-6 weeks), or have not adequately measured iron store markers (such as ferritin) or hepcidin. There is also variability in definitions of IDA, iron doses used, and assessment of adherence.^{13,14} These limit the generalizability of results to many settings including Pakistan.

Accordingly, this study was designed to compare daily vs alternate-day oral iron therapy over an 8-week period among adults with confirmed iron deficiency anemia, evaluating both hematologic response (hemoglobin), iron store replenishment (ferritin), side-effect profiles, and adherence. By doing so in a Pakistani tertiary hospital, we aim to provide local, clinically relevant evidence to guide best practices in this high prevalence setting.

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

This comparative cross-sectional study was conducted in the Department of Medicine, Federal Government Polyclinic Hospital (FGPC), Islamabad, after approval by the Institutional Ethics Committee. The study was carried out over four months, from March 2025 to June 2025. All participants provided written informed consent prior to enrollment, and data were anonymized to maintain confidentiality. Sample size estimation using the WHO calculator indicated a minimum of 55 patients per group to detect a clinically meaningful difference in hemoglobin rise with 80% power and a 5% significance level. To account for potential attrition, 60 participants were recruited per group, giving a total of 120 patients.

The study included adult patients aged 18–60 years with a confirmed diagnosis of iron deficiency anemia (IDA) based on laboratory criteria: hemoglobin <12 g/dL in females or <13 g/dL in males, serum ferritin <30 ng/mL, and microcytic hypochromic indices on peripheral smear. Patients were eligible if they were newly diagnosed or previously untreated for IDA. Individuals with anemia due to other causes (vitamin B12 or folate deficiency, chronic kidney disease, hemolysis, or chronic inflammatory disorders), recent blood transfusion, pregnancy, lactation, or ongoing acute illness were excluded. A total of 120 eligible patients were consecutively recruited and randomly allocated into two equal groups (n = 60 each):

- Group A: Received daily oral iron therapy (ferrous sulfate 200 mg once daily, equivalent to 60 mg elemental iron).
- Group B: Received alternate-day oral iron therapy (ferrous sulfate 200 mg every other day).

All participants were advised to take the medication on an empty stomach with water and to avoid tea, coffee, or calcium-rich foods for at least one hour before and after ingestion. No additional iron supplementation or parenteral therapy was administered during the study period.

Each participant was followed for eight weeks. Compliance was assessed at follow-up visits using pill counts and patient self-reports, and adherence $\geq 80\%$ was considered satisfactory. Patients were counseled to report any adverse effects, particularly gastrointestinal (GI) symptoms such as nausea, constipation, or abdominal discomfort.

Baseline demographic and clinical characteristics, including age, sex, and body mass index (BMI), were recorded. Blood samples were collected at baseline and at eight weeks to measure hemoglobin and serum ferritin levels. All laboratory tests were performed in the

institutional laboratory using standardized procedures with routine internal quality controls. The primary outcome was the change in hemoglobin (ΔHb) from baseline to 8 weeks. Secondary outcomes included the proportion of patients achieving an Hb rise ≥ 2.0 g/dL, change in serum ferritin levels, and treatment adherence. The frequency of gastrointestinal adverse events (nausea, constipation, abdominal pain) and treatment discontinuation due to adverse effects were also recorded.

Data were analyzed using SPSS version 23.0 (IBM Corp., Armonk, NY, USA). Continuous variables were expressed as mean \pm standard deviation (SD) for normally distributed data or median (interquartile range) for skewed data. Categorical variables were summarized as frequencies and percentages. Between-group comparisons were made using the independent-samples t-test or Mann-Whitney U test for continuous variables, and the chi-square test or Fisher's exact test for categorical variables. A two-tailed p-value < 0.05 was considered statistically significant.

RESULTS:

A total of 120 patients with iron deficiency anemia were enrolled, comprising 60 patients in the daily iron group and 60 in the alternate-day iron group. Both groups were comparable at baseline in terms of demographic and clinical characteristics (Table 1). The mean age of participants was 37.0 ± 9.8 years in the daily group and 36.4 ± 10.2 years in the alternate-day group ($p = 0.74$). Females constituted the majority of the study population (76.7% in the daily group vs. 75.0% in the alternate-day group, $p = 0.84$). Mean body mass index (BMI) was similar across both groups (25.1 ± 3.7 vs. 25.0 ± 3.6 kg/m², $p = 0.91$). Baseline hemoglobin and ferritin levels did not differ significantly between the two groups ($p = 0.56$ and $p = 0.67$, respectively).

Table 1. Baseline characteristics of participants (n = 120)

CHARACTERISTIC	DAILY IRON (N = 60)	ALTERNATE-DAY IRON (N = 60)	p-VALUE*
Age, years (mean ± SD)	37.0 ± 9.8	36.4 ± 10.2	0.74
Female sex n (%)	46 (76.7%)	45 (75.0%)	0.84
BMI, kg/m ² (mean ± SD)	25.1 ± 3.7	25.0 ± 3.6	0.91
Baseline hemoglobin, g/dL (mean ± SD)	8.7 ± 0.9	8.6 ± 0.8	0.56
Baseline ferritin, ng/mL median (IQR)	15 (9-22)	14 (8-21)	0.67

* p ≤ 0.05 was considered statistically significant.

After eight weeks of therapy, the alternate-day iron group demonstrated a significantly greater improvement in hematologic parameters compared to the daily therapy group (Table 2). Mean hemoglobin at 8 weeks was 10.7 ± 1.0 g/dL in the alternate-day group versus 10.0 ± 1.0 g/dL in the daily group (p = 0.002). The mean change in hemoglobin from baseline was +2.1 ± 1.0 g/dL in the alternate-day group and +1.3 ± 1.0 g/dL in the daily group (p < 0.001).

A significantly higher proportion of patients in the alternate-day group achieved an Hb rise ≥2.0 g/dL (58.3% vs. 33.3%, p = 0.007). Median ferritin at 8 weeks also showed a superior increase in the alternate-day group (40 [30-52] ng/mL) compared with the daily group (32 [24-42] ng/mL, p = 0.012). Treatment adherence was high in both groups, with no statistically significant difference (93.3% vs. 86.7%, p = 0.21).

Table 2: Hematologic outcomes at 8 weeks

OUTCOME	DAILY IRON (N = 60)	ALTERNATE-DAY IRON (N = 60)	p-VALUE*
Hemoglobin at 8 weeks, g/d (mean ± SD)	10.0 ± 1.0	10.7 ± 1.0	0.002
Change in Hb from baseline, g/dL (mean ± SD)	+1.3 ± 1.0	+2.1 ± 1.0	<0.001
Patients with Hb rise ≥2.0 g/dL – n (%)	20 (33.3%)	35 (58.3%)	0.007
Ferritin at 8 weeks, ng/mL – median (IQR)	32 (24-42)	40 (30-52)	0.012
Adherence ≥80% – n (%)	52 (86.7%)	56 (93.3%)	0.21

* p ≤ 0.05 was considered statistically significant.

Gastrointestinal (GI) adverse effects were more frequent among patients receiving daily iron therapy (Table 3). Overall, 30.0% of patients in the daily group experienced at least one GI adverse event compared to 13.3% in the alternate-day group (p = 0.028). The most commonly reported symptoms were nausea (11.7% vs. 5.0%), constipation (13.3% vs. 5.0%),

and abdominal pain (5.0% vs. 3.3%), though individual symptom differences were not statistically significant. Two participants (3.3%) in the daily group discontinued treatment due to intolerable adverse effects, while no discontinuations occurred in the alternate-day group.

Table 3. Gastrointestinal adverse events

Adverse event	DAILY IRON (N = 60)	ALTERNATE-DAY IRON (N = 60)	p-VALUE*
Any GI event – n (%)	18 (30.0%)	8 (13.3%)	0.028
Nausea – n (%)	7 (11.7%)	3 (5.0%)	0.19
Constipation – n (%)	8 (13.3%)	3 (5.0%)	0.11
Abdominal pain – n (%)	3 (5.0%)	2 (3.3%)	0.65
Discontinuation due to AE – n (%)	2 (3.3%)	0 (0.0%)	0.15

* p ≤ 0.05 was considered statistically significant.

DISCUSSION:

This study compares the efficacy, tolerability, and iron store replenishment of daily versus alternate-day oral iron therapy in adults with iron deficiency anemia. In this study of 120 adult patients with iron deficiency anemia (IDA), alternate-day dosing of oral iron was superior to daily dosing with respect to hemoglobin rise, ferritin increase, and incidence of gastrointestinal (GI) adverse events; adherence was high in both groups with no statistically significant difference. In our study, the mean change in hemoglobin from baseline to 8 weeks was $+2.1 \pm 1.0$ g/dL in the alternate-day group versus $+1.3 \pm 1.0$ g/dL in the daily group ($p < 0.001$), and a greater proportion of patients in the alternate-day group achieved an Hb rise ≥ 2.0 g/dL (58.3% vs. 33.3%, $p = 0.007$). A study by Kaundal et al. compared 60 mg iron twice daily vs. 120 mg alternate day and found more patients in the twice-daily group achieved a ≥ 2.0 g/dL rise by 6 weeks (58% vs. 35.5%, $p = 0.001$), and mean rise was higher (2.9 vs. 2.0 g/dL).¹⁵ Mehta et al. in his study found that by day 21, the alternate-day therapy produced a mean increase in hemoglobin of 1.58 ± 0.53 g/dL, significantly more than the 0.41 ± 0.25 g/dL in the daily therapy group.¹⁴ On the contrary Pasupathy et al. conducted an RCT in 200 adults with Hb ≤ 10 g/dL. They compared alternate-day dosing (120 mg elemental iron every other day) vs. daily single-tablet dosing (60 mg daily) over 8 weeks. They found mean hemoglobin increases of $+1.05 \pm 1.34$ g/dL (alternate-day) vs. $+1.36 \pm 1.51$ g/dL (daily) ($p = 0.47$), i.e., no significant difference between regimens.¹³ These results indicate alternate day

may out-perform daily single dose, perhaps due to improved absorption or less suppression.

In our study, ferritin at 8 weeks (median) was 40 (IQR 30–52) ng/mL in the alternate-day group vs. 32 (24–42) ng/mL in the daily group ($p = 0.012$), indicating superior replenishment of iron stores in the alternate-day group. von Siebenthal HK et al. in his study found that alternate-day dosing did not produce higher serum ferritin than consecutive-day dosing at equivalent total iron exposure, although alternate-day dosing reduced iron deficiency at 6 months and had fewer GI side effects.¹⁶ Caştur L et al. reported significant increases in ferritin and hemoglobin after one month of alternate-day iron in their cohort, though differences across studies were attributed to differing cumulative iron intake and regimen specifics. This study is concordant with your ferritin improvement on alternate-day therapy.¹⁷ Mehta S et al. in a prospective randomized study including hepcidin measurements, alternate-day therapy produced more favourable biochemical responses (including markers related to iron stores) compared with daily dosing; this aligns with our finding of superior ferritin rise and supports a mechanistic role for hepcidin modulation.¹⁴

In our study, the proportion of patients with adherence $\geq 80\%$ was high in both arms (86.7% in daily vs. 93.3% in alternate-day), with no statistically significant difference ($p = 0.21$). A systematic review by Dhanvijay et al. incorporating 11 RCTs (~1014 participants) demonstrated no significant difference in hemoglobin outcomes between daily and alternate-day oral iron regimens; however, alternate-day dosing was associated with better

tolerability and fewer adverse effects.¹⁸ Similarly, Kamath et al. found reduced frequency of GI symptoms such as nausea and altered bowel habits with alternate-day dosing in a pooled sample of 594 participants.¹⁹ Moreover, Mehta et al. reported that alternate-day therapy led to improved biochemical response and a favorable side-effect profile, supporting the potential for improved adherence with intermittent schedules.¹⁴

The limitations of the study included that it was conducted at a single center, which may limit the generalizability of the results to broader or more diverse populations. The follow-up duration of eight weeks, while sufficient to assess early hematologic response, may not fully capture long-term iron store repletion or relapse rates after discontinuation of therapy. Hepcidin levels were not measured; therefore, the proposed mechanistic explanation for improved absorption with alternate-day dosing could not be directly evaluated.

CONCLUSION:

In adults with iron deficiency anemia, alternate-day oral iron therapy was associated with a significantly greater hemoglobin response, superior replenishment of iron stores, and a lower incidence of gastrointestinal adverse events compared with conventional daily dosing. Given its simplicity, cost-effectiveness, and favorable safety profile, alternate-day oral iron supplementation represents a practical and potentially superior strategy for the management of iron deficiency anemia in routine clinical practice. Further studies incorporating biomarkers (hepcidin), longer follow-up, and including special populations (pregnant, elderly) are needed to refine dosing schedules.

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